

PUNTO CRÍTICO

SEPTEMBER - OCTOBER 2023
ISSUE 7

PUNTO CRÍTICO

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Editor's note

As humans, we have an enormous capacity to imagine and create. Regardless of our place of origin, beliefs, stories, and trajectories, we have managed to use and transform what surrounds us to make countless things that respond to our needs. It is in this creative potential that art has found its space in multiple forms and scales, it is there where art not only transforms but penetrates our ideas, emotions, and connections. In this second edition dedicated to ARTivism, you will find a note by Alessandro Zagato, from Artists at Risk Connection, about indigenous art and activism in Latin America; we also present you a note from Eduardo Hernández, an architect specialized in concrete technologies, who talks about an essential material for humanity. Then, we have an interview in *CO2NVERSING* with Gold Power, a Colombian artist who is a pioneer in using waste gold from mines and electronics for her paintings and art pieces. In the *YES YES IT IS* section, we share a "gallery" with a Zapatista story and short text, a photograph by Iván García (diver and photographer), and a couple of paintings by Gold Power. At the end, you have a list of recommendations to *TAKE AWAY*. We hope you enjoy this edition.

CDMX, México.
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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8357451

INDIGENOUS ART AND ACTIVISM IN LATIN AMERICA: IDENTITY, RESILIENCE AND SOCIAL TRANSFORMATION

By **Alessandro Zagato**
Artists at Risk Connection (ARC) - PEN America

*"We are not just artists; we are storytellers,
keepers of traditions and architects of
a cultural renaissance."*

(Antonio Paucar, Peruvian visual artist)

In Latin America, ancient traditions are uniquely intertwined with the contemporary world, giving life to innovative, sometimes even revolutionary, intellectual and artistic perspectives. The legacy of these traditions in the current context is not limited to the mere convergence of different cultural expressions but represents a profound act of introspection and revelation rooted in conflicts, traumas, and approaches that have left their mark on the history of this region. This intersection exemplifies the concept of "border thinking," which, according to Walter Mignolo¹ refers to a space of hybrid knowledge where knowledge and practices emerge from the interaction of apparently incompatible subjectivities. In this sense, indigenous artists emerge as agents of questioning, challenging the rigid borders that have been imposed between Western and indigenous art, thus adopting a perspective that we could characterize as decolonial.

A Transformative Encounter: Art and Territorial and Cultural Defense in Abya Yala²

In May of this year, Artists at Risk Connection, a program of PEN America, convened a two-day workshop titled "Art and Cultural and Territorial Defense in Abya Yala" with the purpose of exploring and discussing the challenges facing indigenous artists, and its peoples and communities in Latin America. The workshop provided a valuable space for dialogue and exchange of experiences between artists, activists, and defenders of cultural rights from 6 different Latin American countries. Its central objective was to exchange information about invisible or subaltern artistic panoramas and provide tools for defending the human rights and freedom of expression of indigenous creators. Likewise, "Art and Territorial and Cultural Defense in Abya Yala" became a favorable setting for the exchange of experiences and works of several indigenous artists, who addressed vitally important issues, such as identities, equality in the artistic union, defense of ancestral territories and cultures against processes of dispossession and appropriation, contemporary forms of colonialism and dialogue between communities and national and international institutions.

¹ Walter Mignolo. *Habitar la frontera. Sentir y pensar la descolonialidad* (Antología, 1999-2014). Barcelona Center for International Affairs, Universidad Autónoma de Ciudad Juárez, 2015.

² Abya Yala is the name given to America by the Kuna people before the arrival of Christopher Columbus and the Europeans. It means "land in full maturity" or "land of vital blood."

The Context: San Cristóbal de Las Casas and the Zapatista Movement

This event took place in San Cristóbal de Las Casas, Chiapas, Mexico, in a territory inhabited by different indigenous peoples and marked by deep historical conflicts linked to colonization and by resistance movements whose actions have resonated in all latitudes. Among them, the most important is the Zapatista movement, which in its long history, has distanced itself in many aspects from traditional forms of resistance. It has done so by opening autonomous spaces - at a creative distance from the state - and constantly experimenting with innovative ideas and original strategic perspectives, in many cases through art and true staging in public space. In the last decade, this movement has placed an unprecedented emphasis on community art and creative production processes in which the figure of the "collective" is expressed and stands out, largely displacing the artistic individualities that belong to the conception of Western art since the Renaissance and that are exalted by the contemporary market. In the context of a civilizational crisis that, as Amador Fernández Savater³ has shown, offers neither turning back nor escapes forward, art from indigenous peoples can open a fork from which to sustain other worlds here and now.

Identity, Resilience, and Creativity: Indigenous Art as a Witness to History

In this context of tensions, the workshop "Art and Territorial and Cultural Defense in Abya Yala" demonstrates an intricate interaction between identity and artistic expression, which manifests itself as a process in search of empowerment, cultural reaffirmation, and recognition. The tensions between traditional notions of art and more contemporary forms of artistic expression become manifest. As Julieth Morales, a Misak artist from Colombia, eloquently noted: "In every weave, in every wood carving, and in every brushstroke, we leave a mark that transcends time." This statement demonstrates the resilience rooted in contemporary indigenous cultural production and the determination of indigenous peoples to preserve cultural bases in an environment characterized by processes of constant evolution. In this sense, indigenous art becomes a witness to history, a chronicle of resistance and survival. Each work of art is a living testimony that transcends the canvas, the sculpture, or the platform, penetrating the collective consciousness of Latin America. It is a call to preserve cultural wealth, challenge stereotypes, and embrace the resilience that permeates every stroke, reminding us that art is a reflection of our shared humanity.

PH Joel, a Tseltal artist from Chiapas, pointed out that indigenous art is not only presented as a form of aesthetic expression but as a testimony of the resilience, strength, and unbreakable identity of native cultures.

In this context, indigenous art is not merely a tool of creative expression but a powerful field of resistance that challenges and counteracts the historical marginalization that has affected these communities over time. According to Joel, "Art is more than pigments and brushes; it is an echo of our stories and a cry for our identity." Workshop participants advocated for **dialogue between worlds and cultures**, challenging prejudices and building a bridge to artistic universality. Seba Calfuqueo, a Mapuche artist from Chile, highlighted the need to **overcome the quantitative view** often applied to representatives of indigenous peoples in art exhibitions and events, which she sees as merely "dues" to pay off a colonial debt.

It must be considered that indigenous artists operate in a delicate balance between the expectations of their communities and the demands of contemporary art and culture institutions. Traditional artistic expressions undoubtedly possess immense cultural value, but at the same time, contemporary art forms are equally essential to express ever-evolving indigenous identities and productions. However, it is common for communities to face difficulties when trying to understand and appreciate the importance of contemporary works, highlighting the need to sensitize both communities and institutions about the diverse evolution of indigenous art.

In this way, indigenous artists find themselves in a **dichotomy**. On the one hand, they face the imposition of Western models and the lack of understanding on the part of non-indigenous curators. On the other hand, they seek to maintain their authentic cultural narratives, which presents unique challenges to asserting their own personal creative authenticity. This dilemma highlights the importance of fostering respect and understanding between artists, communities, curators, and institutions.

³ Amador Fernández Savater. "Una fuerza vulnerable: el malestar como energía de transformación social". El Diario. 27 de Enero 2016.

Amid these challenges, the workshop resonated with the urgency of collaboration and solidarity. **Indigenous artists need to gain strength in unity to amplify their voices and convey their messages.** Networks of creativity intertwine, transcending geographic borders and cultural barriers. Through cooperation, indigenous peoples can consolidate themselves as agents of change for our societies. **Art, from indigenous peoples, is conceived as a heuristic, imaginative, and productive field.**

In general, artistic expressions present a dimension that, let's put it this way, exceeds, and goes beyond the social-historical context, the culture, the frameworks, the complexities, and the materialities in which they are manifested. This is the transformative function that indigenous peoples attribute and seek in it. **Art always has an open side**, a gap in the historical conditions of its production. It is from this opening towards the field of the possibility that new encounters and subjectivities can develop. This is a fundamental task in a situation like the current one that seems blocked between a world in ruins and another that is still taking time to be born. A social context where we have been left without horizons, with an uncertain future, and few mobilizing hopes. This is a moment when, as Shakespeare noted, **"everything solid melts into air."**

However, this uncertainty should not be seen simply as an obstacle but as fertile ground for the generation of new ideas and social configurations. To build them, we must work from the dispersed and chaotic elements that remain in the wake of the disappearance of dualisms and great past narratives. Through their artistic production and forms of resistance, indigenous peoples are demonstrating remarkable creativity by using these dispersed elements and fusing them with their own worldview, ancestral knowledge, and solidarities.

In Latin America, aesthetic sensitivity and artistic expression have been revealed as essential instruments in the construction of new proposals and paths, such as that of the Zapatista towns of Chiapas or the Mapuche communities of the extreme south of the continent. Art, in all its forms, acts as a powerful language that can communicate ideas and values in ways that go beyond words. Through art, complex concepts can be explored and expressed, and people's emotional fibers can be touched, allowing us to turn present crises into the construction of other possible worlds. This implies the search for other ways of relating to work, the body, language, the land, the city, and the community.

The workshop *"Art and Territorial and Cultural Defense in Abya Yala"* reminds us that indigenous art goes beyond being a simple aesthetic manifestation. It is a beacon that illuminates the path toward a future that is inclusive and respectful of cultural diversity. In this brief journey, we have explored a territory where ancestral cultural roots intertwine with contemporary creativity, generating perspectives and expressions that challenge conventional narratives. This phenomenon, rooted in the convergence of cultures and historical conflicts, highlights the ability of artists to transcend traditional divisions between Western art and indigenous art. In addition to its artistic dimension, indigenous art is presented as a vibrant testimony of resilience and strength, an echo of identities that have survived historical marginalization and processes of dispossession and extermination. **As a tool of resistance and a call for cultural preservation, indigenous art emerges as a powerful voice in the construction of a new artistic and social paradigm.**

IN CONCRETE:

THE PERSPECTIVE OF AN ESSENTIAL MATERIAL

By **Eduardo Hernández Guerrero**

Architect specializing in concrete technologies

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Since the first human settlements and their subsequent transformation into civilizations with population centers and sumptuous religious or political enclosures, human beings have interacted with and modified their environment through the processes of extraction and transformation of construction materials that have been fundamental for the development of their buildings, always seeking larger scales or ostentation. The possibility of obtaining raw materials for construction has represented an opportunity for humanity to create a refuge and a way of growth and expansion. This has generated large geographical strongholds for all civilizations, as well as the ability to provide goods and shelter to people and develop various socio-economic activities.

Throughout history, the mastery and advancement of technology in conjunction with construction materials have been the differentiator between civilizations as a sign of their power through their buildings. Some of these great works are present to date, which shows their durability and efficiency in the management of the materials and techniques used. The great ancient civilizations on all continents created great architectural and infrastructure works that allowed them to position themselves at the pinnacle of economic and political power. The search for and obtaining more durable and ostentatious materials, regardless of their origin or the distance from which they had to be transported, created a status quo concentrated in the great capitals of the world.

These practices have had a great impact on nature in many ways for centuries. If we take as reference some of the current practices, we can realize the irreversible effects of extractive processes to which we can today add the generation of large carbon emissions associated with industrial activities and the transportation of materials. It seems that the dynamics over time have changed very little.

The different materials for construction have given way to eras where construction activity and mastery in its transformation process marked trends or architectural styles. As Mies van der Rohe¹ said: "*Technology and architecture are exponents of their time.*" Thus, materials such as mortar, pozzolans, stone, marble, and wood have determined the shapes, geometries, and construction methods.

On October 21, 1824, in England, a builder from Leeds, Joseph Aspdin, was granted British patent BP 5022 entitled "*An innovation in the mode of producing artificial stone,*" to which Aspdin gave the name "*Portland cement.*" From this work and later at the end of the same century, supported by the research² of the Frenchman Henry Le Châtelier, the first steps of what is known today as **the modern era of cement** and the emergence of concrete as a construction material were taken.

In the 20th century, these advances supported by the industrial production of cement with a boom in Europe in the interwar period for the reconstruction of cities and the industrial consolidation of the United States made the use of cement as a raw material consolidate **the concrete era**. This occurred due to three main factors:

- Obtaining raw materials;
- Industrial production;
- The replicability of the process to manufacture concrete and its cost.

Concrete became the first option for fast, resistant, and economical construction anywhere in the world. Its manufacture is simple due to the benefits of Portland cement, and its processes are currently adopted throughout the planet. Thanks to its use in large infrastructure and building works, cities have been able to satisfy the economic growth and populations that increase year after year.

For more than a century, the essential components of concrete are 4: cement, water, fine aggregates, and coarse aggregates. Currently, the technology of this material cannot do without using chemical additives to improve or confer other properties to the mixtures to meet the construction demands both in the fresh state and in the hardened state of the material. Based on this, the evaluation of the environmental impact of concrete considers the high demand for cement, water, and aggregates obtained by the exploitation of surface banks or extractive mining, in addition to the emissions and waste generated through the various industrial processes and transportation involved. In summary, to obtain, manufacture, and transport concrete, a large number of raw materials and non-renewable elements are required that can directly affect the degradation of nature and directly disrupt the environmental and social balance from which they are obtained.

It is estimated that the current demand for concrete is 35,000 million tons per year and is increasing every year. This number implicitly has substantial direct impacts on the entire production chain, as well as a large amount of global emissions into the atmosphere, considering that approximately 3% of these correspond to the cement industry. One fact to consider is that for every kilogram of concrete produced, 166 grams of CO₂ are emitted³.

¹ Mies van der Rohe was a German architect, director of the Bauhaus from 1930 to 1933, and one of the great exponents of the modern movement.

² Research in the composition of hydraulic mortars, Henry Le Châtelier, 1887.

³ Hannah Ritchie, Max Roser and Pablo Rosado (2020) - "CO₂ and Greenhouse Gas Emissions". Published online at OurWorldInData.org. Retrieved from: '<https://ourworldindata.org/co2-and-greenhouse-gas-emissions>' [Online Resource]

It is a fact that with the projections of global growth and construction of population environments that the UN predicts in its Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) report, the use of concrete will not decrease in this century. As of today, there is no material that can satisfy the demands of the contemporary world, and it is difficult to imagine a short-term solution that could stop its use altogether. Therefore, it is important to analyze this problem from different fronts and put into perspective the role of this material in reference to the needs and interests of a corporate, commercial, scientific, and socio-economic nature if what we are looking for is more sustainable and innovative ways for its manufacturing and use, and with a smaller environmental and social footprint.

Can we imagine a different future for this material, which is essential for our societies?

I think so. Concrete is the most consumed construction material on the planet, and there are entire fields of research around each of its components, with multiple regulations and standards for its use. So, the options to innovate and improve its use and manufacturing are enormous, wide-ranging, and impactful. However, it is important to analyze each of these efforts and the why and why of those who manage and promote them.

For large companies in the cement and concrete industry, it is essential to maximize the benefits that supply and demand establish. Although there are other materials on the market (such as steel, wood, etc.), large cement and concrete companies should not worry about the demand for their product since the need for them is imminent. It is clear that business will not decline and that this industry represents, to a certain extent, a safe bet on **"gray gold."** This forces them to be more efficient in internal processes, optimize the use of raw materials that are increasingly difficult to obtain, and commit to comprehensive sustainability throughout the production chain, while at the same time, they must minimize impacts on the environment. and establish itself as a more resilient industry in the face of the effects of climate change in the different environments where they operate and operate.

These companies must respond to increasingly strict regulations to have clean and efficient operations, which has effects on the associated costs, forcing them to undertake a search for innovations in cement-concrete to be sustainable and competitive.

Large investments in marketing to publicize its *"green"* options, position themselves as a *"socially responsible"* company, or provide dubious labels in order to give legitimacy to its products tend to lead to **"greenwashing"**, which is an increasingly common practice more recurrent. Behind these initiatives, there are multiple corporate objectives and interests to not compromise their profits and pass on to end customers not only the costs associated with the *"solutions"* they provide but also a sense of guilt for consuming *"unsustainable"* materials and with it increase profits through *"green"* products.

It is important that all of us who use concrete for various purposes, whether in design, construction, or study, consider the new technologies available for its production and use, as well as the cost-benefit in time and human-material resources. There is also a responsibility to be consumers, especially when building work provides us with basic benefits for our well-being and the development of daily activities.

In the future, as well as in the present, concrete will continue to be a part of our lives. Therefore, it is essential that we focus our efforts on creating synergies to make better processes and use of materials not only as a core part of large infrastructure works but also in rural environments where there is a wide possibility of combining other forms of knowledge, experience, and materials that can be enriched and fed back with new raw materials and construction technologies. There is a great possibility of developing architectural and infrastructure processes that are sustainable, have less impact on the environment, and are more respectful of social and cultural environments without falling into the trap of absolutist and radical models.

Simón Vélez, one of the greatest exponents of bamboo architecture, explained that the increase in the use of Guadua⁴ was largely due to the use of concrete in the hollow structural nodes of bamboo, allowing more effective interactions and mechanical possibilities in these buildings⁵.

"My proposal as an architect is to make architecture a little more vegetarian - not so much concrete - but not totally vegetarian either. You must have a balanced diet between minerals and vegetables and we are too mineral with architecture..."

(Simón Vélez, Colombian architect)

I am excited to think about the future of concrete and its wide possibilities in a simile with literary and fictional works taken to film such as *Blade Runner*, *Foundation*, or *Ready Player One*, where this material continues to be presented as part of the imagination of young and old. buildings, as close to us as until now. For this to be possible, we must leave aside *"short-term"* visions and the limited idea of using a single material and let our imagination and creativity fly to develop projects and works where the diversity of visions, materials, and futures can be built.

⁴ Guadua is a plant from the bamboo family, which provides great benefits to the land and people, since almost all the elements of a house can be built with it.

⁵ José Tomás Franco. "Arquitectura en Bambú: la obra de Simón Vélez" 04 jun 2013. ArchDaily México. Accedido el 20 Ago 2023. <<https://www.archdaily.mx/mx/02-265878/arquitectura->

ABOUT MINING, TECHNOLOGY, AND ART

Interview with **Gold Power Vélez**
By **Jazmín Mota y Lorena Morales**

In this interview, we talk with Gold Power Vélez, a Colombian-Canadian geologist, historian, archaeologist, artisanal miner, and pioneer in the history of plastic art in the use of gold, diamonds, and many other precious metals and minerals reused in her different art pieces. Through her work, Gold Power encourages the reuse of minerals usually discarded in mining or electronic devices that are produced at greater speed and in greater quantities every day. During this talk, Gold tells us part of her long history and different moments in her life in which art, combined with many other things and circumstances, has become a powerful tool to transform herself and become *"her own piece of art."*

L: Gold, could you tell us about how you became a pioneer in the use of mineral waste to transform it into art?

G: It's a long story that goes back 50 years. I was born to a Chocuanos father, a black man from the Colombian Pacific, and to my white mother, a life designer and also a seamstress, who had several jobs: my father had a hardware store while he was president of the community, he also worked in several movie theaters and as a waiter at "Patio Bonito" in Medellín. As if that were not enough, he sold medicinal plants on the weekends and ended the week traveling to towns to play street gambling games to adjust his money to provide for his 3 little daughters. My mother, although she only studied until third grade, was not far behind in how to get the money necessary to buy a little house in a safer neighborhood for her little ones. Her few years of study were enough for her to learn to read and love her books in her free time as a seamstress and embroidered beautiful dresses for the beauty queens of Colombia and Venezuela.

As presidents of communal action, my parents began to build the neighborhood where I was born, a neighborhood of great poverty and perhaps the most controversial in Colombia.

I learned as a child to crawl and walk carrying debris. I think that from there, I began to delve into the many things there are to do and think about on this planet. Carrying debris, learning art, the gift of crawling and walking in dry mud and dirt, building little houses, and meanwhile reading Nietzsche, Cervantes, and Jules Verne, in addition to all the Marvel comics that my parents were fans of, were these family and neighborhood atmosphere that guided me since then to build stories with the objects, customs, habits that were interwoven around me.

My first introduction to precious metals was when I asked my parents how a light bulb worked, and they told me: *"Because it has gold, silver, and copper,"* and they started a whole discussion about what the minerals were and how they were used. My dad told me, "I'm going to take you where there is gold," and he introduced me to the Chocó area, not only the rainiest area on the planet but one of the most impenetrable jungles, El Darién, also the richest in gold. Between these inhospitable jungles of Darien and the "jungle" of a neighborhood marked by poverty and violence, I spent the first 12 years of my life. And so began my path to being a pioneer in what I do.

J: How would you say that this relationship with your environment, with nature, with your community shaped this project you are working on?

G: Since I was little, I was a pretty restless girl, kind of a “genius” who wanted to know the reason for everything. I learned to read at a very young age in a community where the least interesting thing was reading. My friends and my environment were full of many problems of weapons and violence. I grew up in a neighborhood full of hitmen, and I had to see a lot of deaths, many crises, and between one and the other, a great dilemma in what to do to help my little friends and not seeing them die in shootouts and gang revenge.

Something that I have not told before is how I learned carpentry: at the age of 6 years old, I learned with a *changón*¹ that a friend built, when he showed it to me when he fired it, that gun changed my life. So I told my friend “*Teach me how to carve wood,*” and instead of making a weapon, I made puppets. With them I began to give puppet performances in the window of the little ranch that was already becoming a home, perhaps imitating my parents who ventured into the cinema where we lived and projected films on the walls of the new houses and the renovated neighborhood that - it is worth mention - he knew nothing about architectural design. I found how to tell stories to these kids who were so upset with life, and I became a storyteller in the midst of extreme violence and poverty. It is incredible to think today that in a region so rich in natural resources, there was and still is so much poverty and violence.

When I started going to the areas of El Darién and Chocó, I didn't know the minerals very well, but I asked the miners “*And why are you throwing away all those minerals?*” because I saw how much of the material that was extracted was wasted.

My parents also told me that gold was in televisions and other devices... it was enough information to get me interested in studying computer analysis and programming at the age of 16 and start searching for these precious metals in electronic devices of all kinds. When I was 18, I opened a company with a friend, and we brought computers from the US. I asked our technician to leave the useless computers so that I could, in my free time, extract gold and other metals and minerals that usually go to the trash.

The activities he did allowed me to interact with the wealthiest people in the area, and I began to see waste on the one hand and lack on the other, something that has nothing to do with having or not having money. What I saw was a lot of waste, especially with the development and adoption of technology. I started to get into the topic of art because I consider it to be the most open means to be able to reach any type of person and tell them, “*Be careful with your forms and consumption practices!*”

¹ The name *changón* is a derivative of the English expression “shut gun”; in this case the *changón* was made of wood but it can be made of different materials.

L: What impact do you think your work has had on society?

G: It depends on what we call impact. I don't see myself as a well-known famous person; rather, I have dedicated myself to traveling the planet to talk to people. Whatever is happening in your life and on this planet, you have to understand that the problems we face are no one's but mine, yours, they are problems that are repeated in this thing we call humanity. Both you and I are human, and that makes us equal; different is what you do, think, believe, and experience. I do not consider that anyone has to listen to you - much less reject you - because you are a woman, a man, non-binary, not because you are poor, rich, nor because of your skin color, your religious beliefs, your political party, your sexual choices, etc., you must be listening because you have something to express from your human experience. We are losing focus that we are humans in the same house, planet Earth, and that is why what you have to say matters.

But getting back to the problems in the world, those problems are mine and yours. It's not what the government, a company, or anyone else does. You decide what you do, what you spend your time on, what you spend and use your money on. You are the community, the government, and the company, you are (as an individual) the decision-maker. For example, we all point everywhere and hear, "They are destroying the planet; those Colombians, Ecuadorians, Brazilians, and Venezuelans finishing the Amazon are backward," but that is said by someone sitting comfortably in front of their computer, a cell phone, in their apartment. This is said by someone who has just bought a table, some cosmetics, a book, and an edible product labeled "organic" in virtual stores and believes they is the "savior of the planet" because they no longer uses plastic but cardboard. They have no problem spending hours criticizing how others are destroying the planet and do not spend five minutes seeing that to have what they have, and to satisfy their desires for products, there, on the other side of the planet, many trees had to be cut down and many miners worked hours without rest to fulfill all their wishes.

I am not a revolutionary, but I make my own revolution. I believe that on this planet, we come to enjoy what we have, not to end it. We must help rethink and propose new trends of thought in the government, with our friends, in our community, that is our planet. It's the place where you live and the people you live with. We can contribute in very small things, from bringing your own cup to the cafeteria and asking for your coffee to be served there; all actions count.

J: It seems to me that these contrasts that you tell us about, the diversity that you have had in your life and what you have done, are also present in your works where there is a mixture of materials that are waste from mining, but also from electronic devices, and art materials. Is this intentional, or has it emerged, or how did you decide to mix these different elements?

G: Everything is planned. Everything we do creates a personal story. Mine goes from the box of tomatoes and the folded clothes as my first mattress - where I slept on as a child -, with my puppets in a neighborhood of hitmen, or my passage through the area of lower Cauca where I have seen since I was a child, and until recently, the dynamics of "one ton minus one gram" of mining where many minerals are wasted and could be extracted by unemployed women and men in the area and used for that great challenge of today that they call "the energy transition," which requires many of those minerals.

My artwork includes the carpentry that I learned from my encounter with a changón and that now allows me to make the frames for my paintings; also what I learned from a couple of people, an Italian and a Greek - who scolded me for everything - who taught me Venetian plaster and art restoration techniques. But I don't have a particular technique but rather what I have been collecting from knowledge and experiences in my life. Of course, my work reflects the story of my life. Your life is your piece of art.

All my artwork is different because I am not the same. I believe that no human can be a single thing, we are an intertwining of everything we experience: what we buy, what we use, what we share. The decisions we make and

how we react also influence what surrounds us and the people around us.

I am the first woman on the planet, in the history of art, who uses gold extracted from technology to talk about environmental issues... that is also me; I am nothing more than another human being who visits this planet and hopes to collect a little wisdom from it and from any living being that I come across in my journey.

If you want to know more about the work of Gold Power Vélez you can contact her through her social media (IG @goldpowerone FB @Gold Power Velez) or through her representative Michelle Marisa Truzzi (FB @Michelle Marisa Truzzi Tiebsch).

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

Story

Popular Zapatista culture

The little tree and the others

Once upon a time, there was a little tree that was very lonely but very willing to decorate and sing in the other's garden.

So there was the little tree, and then the other one came to look at it and take it. But it turns out that the other was not another but others. The others wanted to take the tree to their respective gardens, but there was only one tree, and the others were several others. The little tree was ready to be planted in all the orchards, but there was only one little tree, and the others were several others. Then the others began to discuss who would keep the tree to take to their garden. And one of the others said that he carried it because he was more other than the others. And the other one of the others said no, he was carrying the little tree because he had a prettier garden, etc., and another one said that he was better off because he was a mere gardener and who better than him to take care of the little tree and that's how they were. They fought for a while and did not reach any agreement on unity because although they were others, they did not respect the other who was theirs but was another. And then they ended up fighting and said that everyone would take a piece of the tree.

Then the little tree spoke and said like this: "I don't agree because, in addition to the fact that we shouldn't go around cutting down trees because it threatens the ecological balance, no one is going to win.

Image: Beatriz Aurora

If one of you takes my branches, and another takes the trunk, and the other takes the root, and each one takes his piece to his garden, then it will not turn out well."

"Whoever carries the branches and plants them will not have anything because they do not have the trunk to support themselves or the roots to feed themselves. Whoever carries the trunk will not have anything either because, without branches or roots, the trunk will not be able to breathe or feed. Whoever has the root is the same because, without a trunk or branches, the root will not be able to grow or breathe. Yes, on the other hand, if we make a good agreement between all of us, I can plant myself for a while in one's garden and then another time in the other's garden, and so on. In this way, everyone will have fruits and seeds in each and every one of the gardens." The others were left thinking.

-Tan-tan-

The subcommander hummed the song that says "My father and I planted it at the edge of the patio where the house ends, etc."

The Flower of the Word Will Not Die

The hidden face of the one who names it may die, but the word that came from the depths of history and the Earth can no longer be torn away by the arrogance of power.

We were born of the night, we live in it, we will die in it; but tomorrow the light will be for the most, for all those who mourn the night today, for whom the day is denied, for whom death is a gift, for whom life is prohibited.

For everyone the light, for everyone everything, for us the joyful rebellion, for us nothing.

From the Zapatista Oventic Caracol walls
Chiapas, México.

Iván García

Diver, photographer, and illustrator
IG @spino_uwphoto
Quintana Roo, México

Since I was a child, I liked to watch documentaries on TV and contemplate all the wonders that exist in nature; I dreamed of one day living it beyond the screen. As I grew older, I began to travel to different places, some more spectacular than others; without a doubt, I knew it was something I wanted to continue doing.

At university, I discovered the world of diving. Thanks to it I have been able to visit wonderful and spectacular places that have made me aware of the fragility and importance of nature and these sacred spaces.

Photography is a form of art that represents for me a window into what my eyes have seen, and that allows me to share it with other people in the hope that one day we will be a more conscious and responsible majority dedicated to the care and conservation of natural wonderful places that we still have left.

Paint

Gold Power Vélez

IG @goldpowerone

FB @Gold Power Velez

Secrets of life

Dimensions: 1.57 x 1.26 m

Mixed technique

Materials: Venetian plaster, metallic paint, oil and acrylic. Waterproof resin on plaster; pine frame.

Gold: Reused gold from discarded equipment, computers, and cell phones, 14k, 18k, and 23.99k gold sheets.

Started in 1990 in Medellín, Colombia, and completed in 2017 in Toronto, Canada.

From the **Blossom** collection.

This work is inspired by 10 years of direct studies by the artist Gold Power Velez in the 5 most influential religions of human belief (Judaism, Catholicism, Islam, Buddhism, Tibetans, and other religious practices). This work seeks to express that, as in life itself, beneath the work there is another work; and on top of the work a pair of diamonds. What painting is under the flowers? The artist prefers to keep it a secret. Whoever observes the work can see with the naked eye some dancing blue flowers that reveal their rest and calm in the middle of a wild sea. They float in serene peace while the waves torment themselves. Where do these floating butterfly wings travel and where do they come from? A question that was important before today is more the certainty of its irrelevant meaning because the diamond that these flowers carry is the sublime shine that, like a star, leads them safely, marking their own north.

Paint

Treasure

Dimensions: 1.69 x 1 m

Mixed technique

Materials: Acrylic and oil, Venetian plaster, metallic paint, and resin on canvas.

Gold: Reused gold from discarded equipment, computers, and cell phones, 14k, 18k, and 23.99k gold sheets.

Do you want to know more about this work and the artist's vision? We invite you to follow and contact her on social media (IG @goldpowerone, FB @Gold Power Velez) or through her representative @Michelle Marisa Truzzi.

From **Water, the opulence** collection.

This collection is an aerial view of the vast majority of water as it travels around planet Earth. Maelstrom is untimely, aggressive, dangerous and serene. The sublime treasure that drowns, comes and goes, rains, drips, quenches thirst and evaporates. A planet submerged in water, water submerged in land, living beings of millions of species. The most abundant of natural resources... the most controversial, paradoxical human drowning in drops of water.

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

If you liked the topic of this issue, take a look at the recommendations we have for you.

Book: *Decolonizing nature. Contemporary art and politics of ecology*

This book by Demos, T.J., offers a significant and original contribution to the interconnected fields of art history, ecology, visual culture, geography, and environmental policy. Throughout its six chapters, its author addresses the creative proposals of various artists and activists in search of ways of life that combine ecological sustainability, climate justice, and radical democracy at a time like the present in which this is urgently needed.

Book: *An ecological art. Plastic Creation and the Anthropocene*

In this book, Paul Ardenne presents and exhibits the work of several artists whose works (painting, sculpture, film, photography, installations, and websites) represent a fight against environmental disaster. These artists adopt exemplarity as a principle and open a path of hope in the face of the current ecological challenge on which the human species depends.

Book: *The Routledge Companion to Contemporary Art, Visual Culture, and Climate Change*

This volume brings together leading and emerging voices working at the intersection of contemporary art, visual culture, activism, and climate change and addresses key questions such as: why and how art and visual culture, and their ethics and values matter in a world increasingly affected by climate breakdown by bringing a decolonial and climate justice-based approach to the fore.

Video: *Activism through art*

Chris Jordan is a photographer, artist, and environmental activist. His works criticize the consumerism in which the United States is immersed. His work consists, through photographic montages, in making a comparison that awakens in the viewer the feeling that he intends to convey with his compositions. You can see the video in the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fA8avvsybZA&t=7s>

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

If you liked the topic of this issue, take a look at the recommendations we have for you.

Project and documentary: *Terra, the film*

A ninety-minute documentary by Yann Arthus-Bertrand and Michael Pitiot, produced by Hope Production is a tribute to the human species, which clearly shows us that we are still capable of changing our future just by looking at life differently. This is a project in collaboration with Omega and GoodPlanet that you can find out about in the following link:

<https://www.terra.omega/es/terra>

Collaborative Playlist: *ARTivismo Punto Crítico*

We remind you that we have a collaborative playlist of activism songs that the Punto Crítico team has prepared for you. Of course, we invite you to collaborate in its expansion and share it as an ARTivist act.

<https://open.spotify.com/playlist/06w5JNPTv8XYDpCMFRHDy8?si=cc3f4777ab00495f&pt=c6d5a23d52373f52df8c0d1eaa7b7a5>

Podcast: *Activism, Art and Environmental Justice*

A Climate One podcast in which we discuss with several people from various disciplines about the role of art alongside activism to support the cause of environmental justice. You can listen to the podcast through the following link:

<https://www.climateone.org/audio/activism-art-and-environmental-justice>

Publication: *The Mexican Carbon Capture and Storage Platform: Construction of a boundary object for bridging the gaps between contexts, actors, and disciplines*

We share with you this publication that talks about the construction of the Mexican CCS Platform. If you want to know the process of its creation and why it was created, download the paper at the following link:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1750583623001354>

Mexico City, Mexico, 2023